

Viva Palestina Malaysia, Islamic Medical Association of Malaysia and Federation of Islamic Medical Associations in action in the Palestinian Occupied Territories

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In the aftermath of the Gaza massacre on 27 Dec 2008, Malaysian individuals and NGOs united to champion the Palestinian cause. Viva Palestina Malaysia represents a coalition that cuts across racial, religious and political lines. It reflects the humanitarian nature of the crisis in Palestine, which must be shouldered by all responsible citizens of the world.

Our vision is to *'effectuate a just, equitable, prompt and sustainable resolution to the conflict in Palestine.'*

VPM works closely with the Malaysian government's ministries and agencies, local and international NGOs, and have participated in a number of humanitarian convoys to Gaza.

Our closest and most frequent collaboration has been with the Islamic Medical Association of Malaysia (IMAM) and the Federation of Islamic Medical Associations (FIMA)

And with the generosity of fellow Malaysians and supporters globally, VPM has transferred much needed funds and aid for various projects in Palestine and its diaspora. In the recent incursion by Israel on Gaza, VPM has been on the ground serving the needs of the Internally Displaced Palestinians (IDP). The infographic summarize some of our early initiatives to alleviate the sufferings of the IDP.

In cooperation with the government of Malaysia through #OpsIhsan, 3 consignments of relief and humanitarian

materials have been flown to El-Arish, Egypt and into Gaza. With IMAM and FIMA, our doctors are on standby to enter Gaza to provide professional healthcare and relieve the exhausted healthcare professionals in Gaza. In partnership with al-Khidmat Foundation, Pakistan, IMA North America and Gifts of the Givers, South Africa, preparations are underway for the establishment of a field hospital to assist with the management of casualties of the war. War is always complicated with outbreaks of infectious diseases. As it is, Gaza under siege since 2007, has very poor access to safe and clean drinking water, and hygienic sanitary facilities.

The wanton destruction of basic facilities (e.g. the bombing of water desalination plants built by our FIMA Safe Water project) would exacerbate water borne disease transmissions e.g. acute gastroenteritis caused by viruses, and bacteria such as cholera and typhoid. The contaminated air made worse by bombings and ashes from the collapsing buildings, would increase the risk of air borne infections namely pneumonias, tuberculosis and whooping cough.

And with the coming winter months, their homes destroyed and with poor access to warm clothings, blankets and mattresses, winter bugs namely influenza, respiratory syncytial virus (bronchiolitis), adenoviruses would be killer diseases, especially among the very young and old in the poorly ventilated and crowded shelters.

Together, our public health priorities would be:

1. To ensure the ceasefire remains permanent, to empower decent rehabilitation of the healthcare infrastructure and services in Gaza.
2. To ensure adequate and continuous supply of life saving medicines, critical care monitors and devices, array of pharmaceutical supplies, surgical devices and consumables.
3. To allow access of healthcare professionals and allied health staff to relieve the exhausted Gazan doctors, nurses and other allied health workers.
4. To ensure the more severe cases of injuries and burns be transported to the nearest intensive care facilities for best healthcare treatment and outcomes.
5. To provide the internally displaced Palestinians access to clean water and food to prevent starvation and malnutrition which would further compromise their defense against infections
6. Targeted vaccination programs to prevent the spread of vaccine preventable diseases or it's re-emergence eg polio, TB, pertussis
7. To provide access to fuel to operate the water desalination plants, shelter heating systems, ambulances to transfer patients and power generators for hospital functioning.
8. Invest in programs and initiatives aimed at addressing the psychological trauma and long-term effects of violence on children who have witnessed or experienced conflict-related distress.

All international norms of warfare were violated in the present incursion of Gaza. Hospitals were targeted, healthcare professionals and patients were killed, and babies in ICU were left to die.

In excess of 70% of the Gaza infrastructure were either destroyed or brutalised. It is a tall order to restore the healthcare facilities to near normal. To begin with, the Ministry of Health (MOH) services was much compromised by the siege on Gaza since 2007. So the current invasion is an acute on chronic insult to the Gaza, MOH services. The global community spearheaded by the WHO needs to address comprehensively the acute on chronic health crisis in Gaza. An immediate, comprehensive and accurate assessment of the severity of

the destruction and damages to the healthcare services would point the direction as to the priorities in the rehabilitation of the healthcare infrastructure and services. We've done our little bits to mitigate some of the healthcare issues and address mild-moderate health concerns of the internally displaced Palestinians (IDP).

Directly or indirectly, many of our endeavours have been towards restoring and protecting the health of the IDP in Gaza. These included:

1. Mobile medical clinics for our IDP. Apart from treating and caring for their health concerns, it helps to decongest the overwhelmed hospitals which can focus on the more sicker cases.
2. Providing fuel to power the generators in the government and charity hospitals and to the ambulances to transfer the sick patients.
3. Providing medical and surgical supplies to the government and charity hospitals.
4. And to the families, we provided basic essentials such as first aid kits, hygiene kits, baby kits and baby milk products.
5. Ensure adequate nutrition with the provision of food baskets, hot meals, food vouchers and vegetable baskets and a continuous supply of safe and clean water.
6. And in preparation or the coming winter, we sourced warm clothes, blankets and mattresses for the IDPs.

From 7 October-28 Nov 2023, WHO has documented 427 attacks on healthcare in the Occupied Palestinian Territory. The attacks have resulted in 566 fatalities and 758 injuries within the healthcare facilities.

Even during warfare, health facilities are universally designated as safe zones for healthcare professionals and patients and safe haven for refugees seeking shelter. The WHO stated unequivocally that health facilities, HCP and civilians must be protected under all circumstances. We stand in solidarity with the people of Palestine and their families during these challenging times. We hope and pray for a peaceful resolution to the war, where people of all races, religions and political persuasions can live in an environment free from fear, violence, and trauma. We implore the international community to act swiftly to protect the lives, wellbeing and welfare of all people in the Occupied Palestinian Territory.

Appendices

Locations of Water Desalination Plants built by VPM (FIMA Safe Water) in Gaza and the West Bank, Palestine.

VIVA PALESTINA MALAYSIA **FREE PALESTINE AND THE OCCUPATION**

VPM EMERGENCY AID #PRAY4PALESTINE CAMPAIGN

(UPDATED AS OF 24 NOV 2023).

FUNDS RAISED:

RM 3,750,289.91

FUNDS DISBURSED/ALLOCATED: RM 2,850,844.60

 CASH ASSISTANCES FOR 816 FAMILIES				
 450 BABY KITS				
 CLOTHES VOUCHERS FOR 250 FAMILIES				

THANK YOU FOR YOUR GENEROUS DONATIONS!

Funds collected and disbursed by VPM to Gaza, Palestine from the onset of the Israeli incursion on 7 October 2023 until 24 Nov 2023.

Vegetables bought from the farmers in South Gaza, which were packaged for distribution to Internally Displaced Palestinian families

Hot Meals prepared for the IDP in South Gaza shelters by VPM workers

Safe and clean water were distributed to the IDP families in South Gaza.

Mobile Clinics were organized in South Gaza to address the health needs of the sick and injured

Warm clothings were provided to the poor IDP families in South Gaza.